

Ergonomics for service technicians

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Introduction

In this conference contribution an ergonomic training, addressed to employees with different languages, operating in approximately 100 countries will be presented.

Target group is Scania service technicians (mechanics), working with heavy vehicles. This profession is frequently affected by disorders in back, muscles and joints.

At Scania service workshops there are approximately 13.000 service technicians employed at about 1.500 workshops, spread in more than 100 countries.

Aim

The training aims to increase knowledge about load ergonomics - with the aim to influence the attitudes and behaviour so that service technicians are working in a way to reduce risk for disorders in muscles and joints.

Methods

The training for service technicians consists of two parts: e-learning and "On the job training". To avoid the language barrier, our challenge in the e-learning was to convey a clear message without using text or voice.

1. E-learning, length about 8 minutes: Film includes scenes from 12 different operations in workshop. First, a technique that is strenuous for the body is shown - then follows the same operation performed using a better technique with less strain on the body.

<http://host.learnways.com/scania/ergonomics/>

The e-learning can be carried out by computer, e-Reader or Smartphone.

2. "On the job training" - involves transferring the film's ideas and examples to the workplace. For this chapter we have produced a manual where each chapter contains information, poster and discussion questions.

"On the job training" is carried out with a "train the trainer model".

Results

So far we have trained 96 Technical trainers and 1165 service technicians have implemented the e-learning.